

The Ratio of Electromagnetic force and Gravitation Times the Reduced Compton Wavelength of a Proton is Precisely the Diameter of the Observable Universe. Proton leads to Hubble Mass.

Tomáš Ajdari
tomasajdari@gmail.com
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Abstract:

The product of the reduced Compton wavelength of a proton and the ratio of electromagnetic/gravitational force between two electrons is within 1 % of current best estimates for the diameter of the observable universe. A Planck density cube that would hold a proton (charge radius) would have the same weight as all the matter in a Hubble volume. The relative error is about 2 %, if we use the medium estimates for the size of the proton and the Hubble radius. The possible error interval is about 0 - 21 %, depending on the specific method of estimating the Hubble radius and the size of the proton.

Introduction

The ratio of Electromagnetic force and gravitation between two electrons is $R = 4.17 \times 10^{42}$. The 2018 CODATA reduced compton wavelength of a proton is 2.103089×10^{-16} m [1]. The product of these two values is 8.77×10^{26} m or 92.70 billion light years. The current best estimate for the diameter of the observable universe is 92.8 billion light years [2]. The relative error is less than 1 %.

A cube that could fit a proton (charge radius of proton is estimated to be between 0.842 and 0.8775×10^{-15} m, cube side $a = 1.684 - 1.755 \times 10^{-15}$ m) filled at Planck density (5.1550×10^{96} kg/m³) would weigh $2.462 - 2.787 \times 10^{52}$ kg. The average value is 2.625×10^{52} kg.

The Hubble radius is $1.383 \times 10^{26} - 1.281 \times 10^{26}$ m or 14.62 billion - 13.54 billion ly [3]. This translates to a volume of $1.108 \times 10^{79} - 8.803 \times 10^{78}$ m³. The mass density given by Planck18 is 2.6885×10^{-27} kg/m³, ($H = 67.4$ km/s, $\Omega_m = 0.315$). This leads to a mass of $2.978 \times 10^{52} - 2.367 \times 10^{52}$ kg, with the average value of 2.673×10^{52} kg.

The relative disagreement between the average value of 2.625×10^{52} kg obtained from the proton's radius and the value of 2.673×10^{52} kg obtained from the Hubble radius is 1.8 %, the relative disagreement between the lowest value obtained from the proton radius and the largest value for the Hubble radius is 21 %. The relative disagreement between the largest value obtained from the proton radius and the smallest value obtained from the Hubble radius is 18 %. Charge radius of 8.97×10^{-15} m would be precisely compatible with the value obtained from the largest Hubble radius.

Discussion

As can be seen, the size of a proton is related to the matter content of the Hubble volume and the reduced Compton wavelength of a proton is related to the size of the observable universe. As can be seen in previous work, the size of a classical electron is closely related to the mass of the observable universe (within 0.6 %) and the diameter of a "black hole" electron is closely related to the circumference of the observable universe [4]. These relations might be accidental or there might be a common physical mechanism behind the current size of the proton, classical electron and the mass of the observable universe/Hubble volume.

Conclusion

It has been shown that the charge radius of the proton is related to the mass contained within the Hubble volume and that the reduced Compton wavelength of a proton is related to the diameter of the observable universe. It is unknown if this is an accidental result or a sign of a common physical mechanism.

References:

1. <https://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?pcomwlbar>
2. Paul Halpern and Nick Tomasello, Size of the Observable Universe, <https://dx.doi.org/10.22606/adap.2016.13001>
3. Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.06209>
4. Tomáš Ajdari, The Cube of Classical Electron Diameter is Related to the Mass of the Observable Universe. The Derived Volume = Entropy of the Observable Universe. Λ CDM Problems. Black Hole Electron Related to the Mass of the Observable Universe, <https://zenodo.org/record/7235106#.Y3jIPXbMI2x>